

GS15/NE/FH16
(1) (19) (16)

SHERD SHEET

MATCH WITH OTHER CORPORA

CORPUS	WARE DESIGNATION	TYPE DESIGNATION
Reisner HGN, Myc	CRW	

I. TECHNIQUE

A. HAND MADE	1. Hand Modelled	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	2. Coiling	<input type="checkbox"/>	3. Plate Building	<input type="checkbox"/>
	4. Core Moulding	<input type="checkbox"/>	5. Turntable (up. pt.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	6. Other	<input type="checkbox"/>
B. TURNTABLE			C. WHEELMADE			E. CASTING

II. FABRIC

A. TEXTURE OF CLAY

GENERAL:	Coarse <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Medium	Fine
1. Pebble	<input type="checkbox"/>	2. Granule	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Medium	<input type="checkbox"/>	6. Fine	<input type="checkbox"/>
		7. Very Fine	<input type="checkbox"/>
			8. Silt

B. COMPOSITION Type of Clay: Nile Alluvial

TEMPER (General):	Heavy <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Medium	Light
1. Material	Sand particles	Straw - Chaff	Some lime spots
2. Particle Size	to 1mm	Burnt out	white

C. FRACTURE COLOR

General Description
Red to Reddish Grey passing to
Dark Grey in thick part of wall

Munsell

D. HARDNESS Soft (Finger Nail)

E. POROSITY

F. TRANSVERSE STRENGTH

G. PERMEABILITY

III. SURFACE PROPERTIES

A. SURFACE TREATMENT

1. Untreated	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	2. Wheel Finish	<input type="checkbox"/>	a. ribbing	<input type="checkbox"/>
				b. scrapped or shaved	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Hand Finish	a. smoothed	<input type="checkbox"/>	b. polished by burnishing	<input type="checkbox"/>	c. polished by rubbing
	d. scrapped	<input type="checkbox"/>	e. scratched or combed	<input type="checkbox"/>	f. other
4. Coating	a. wash	<input type="checkbox"/>	b. slip	<input type="checkbox"/>	c. glaze

B. SURFACE TEXTURE Very Rough, pitted

C. MECHANICAL CONDITION OF SURFACE (16) Rough - vertical, Finger marks inside wall

D. LUSTER 1. Matte 2. Low 3. Medium 4. High

E. SURFACE COLOR

General Description
RBr on orange side

Munsell

IV. DECORATION

A. TECHNIQUE

1. Incised	<input type="checkbox"/>	2. Impressed	<input type="checkbox"/>	3. Gouged	<input type="checkbox"/>	4. Pinched	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Modelled	<input type="checkbox"/>	6. Moulded	<input type="checkbox"/>	7. Painted	<input type="checkbox"/>	8. Inlaid	<input type="checkbox"/>